

A Study on Prevalence of Post-Partum Depression among Women

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Abstract

Postpartum depression (PPD) is a mixture of physical, emotional and behavioral changes that happen in some women after given birth. PPD is linked to chemical, Social and psychological changes that happen when having the baby. New mothers experience both emotional and physical changes. Hormonal changes, Lack of Sleep, Anxiety and self- image act as the main contributors for depression. Our body and mind go through many changes during and after pregnancy. PPD cannot be prevented or avoided. Every women faces these kind of issues but in some cases it's carried over time. Though there are many forms of illness the three common forms of postpartum affective illness are the blues (commonly called baby blues, maternity blues), postpartum (or postnatal) depression and puerperal (postpartum or postnatal) psychosis. For some women adjusting to the motherhood can be of postpartum depression, which is a type of depression that both parents can experience after the birth of their baby, but it is very common in women.

Key words: PPD, Social, Emotional, Behavioral, Hormonal changes

Introduction

'Mental health is the capacity of the individual, the group and the environment to interact with one another in ways that promote subjective well- being, the optimal development and use of mental abilities (cognitive, affective and relational), the achievement of individual and collective goals consistent with justice and the attainment and preservation of conditions of fundamental equality.'- 1981 WHO.

Maternal Depression is a type of depression that affects many women after or before the birth of the child. There are different categories of maternal depression which include prenatal depression, postnatal depression and postpartum psychosis. In a study conducted by Ertel, Koenen, & Rich-Edwards (2011), researchers estimated one in seven women are diagnosed with postpartum depression within a year of having baby. Postpartum depression is seen in both men and women. From sleepless nights to dilemmas with breast feeding, being a new mum has a number of challenges that most women approach with anticipation. This period is very much prone to the risk for the development of serious mood disorders. All these mood disorders come under the postpartum affective illnesses. According to NHS, Postpartum Depression affects more than 1 in every 10 women within a year after giving birth to their baby. Its symptoms can include the feelings of sadness and anxiety even at an extreme level which can interfere with a woman's ability to care for herself or her family. The present study is designed to find the prevalence rate of postpartum depression among women in Pathanamthitta district

Research Methodology

Research methodology is the specific procedure or

technique used to identify, select, process and analyse information about the topic. Research methodology explains how the entire research is been done such as data collection, sampling and how analyses has been made

Title Of The Study

"A study on prevalence of post-partum depression among women in Pathanamthitta district, Kerala."

Objectives Of The Study

1. To study the demographic details of people with postpartum depression
2. To study on prevalence of postpartum depression among women
3. Estimate the prevalence of depressive symptoms in women after delivery.
4. To identify the risk factors of postpartum depression.

Statement Of The Problem

Postpartum non-psychotic depression is the most common complication of childbearing affecting approximately 10-15% of women and as such represents a considerable public health problem affecting women and families. Studies on postpartum depression had been conducted in rural and urban areas of India, but still the problem exists as it is, prevalence rate is also increasing. Women of India are the main bread earners in the society but are found to be socially and economically deprived and have high rate of literacy, unemployment and social insecurity, which cause high rate of mental problem among these women. Studies had found that women have high level of depression and then other people. According to the culture a women who gave birth to a boy child will have a status in the society, while the women who gave birth to a girl child is considered as inferior. In

postpartum period the emotional instabilities of a mother is mostly seen only as a physical condition rather than a mental state and is ignored. The age of marriage, the gender of the child, stressful life events, lack of social support all these makes women more vulnerable to postpartum depression. Ignoring postpartum depression may lead to postpartum psychosis. Hence the study focus the to estimate the prevalence of depressive symptoms among women and to assess the various factors like education , socio economic status, maternal age, gender of the child and their in causing postpartum depression.

Research Design

A research design is the set of methods and procedures used in collecting and analyzing measures of the variables specified in the research problem. The researcher used descriptive research design to find out prevalence of postpartum depression among and to know the risk factors associated with it.

Universe and Sampling Method

The universe of this study was women after delivery, mostly from those within 1year of delivery and respondents were taken from Pathanamthitta district. The sample size of this study was 60 women after delivery in Pathanamthitta district, Kerala and the researcher has made use of Convenience sampling method as the technique.

Tools of Data Collection

The researcher had chosen to use Questionnaire Schedule as a tool to data collection from the samples. The questionnaire includes socio-demographic details Edinburg postpartum depression rating scale and WHOQOL Bref scale(for quality of life) to assess the associated factors. The data was collected and analyzed with the help of SPSS package.

Table No. 1 Distribution of age of respondents

Age	No. of respondents	Percentage
Less than 18 years	2	3
18-20 years	8	13
20- 30 years	33	55
Above 30 years	17	29
Total	60	100

Above table shows the age of the respondents. It interfered that out of the total 60 respondents 55% of them were under the age group of 20 – 30 years,

Review Of Literature

Sara M. Sylvén, May 2011 in a study “Seasonality patterns in postpartum depression”. The main objective of the study was to investigate the possible association between postpartum depressive symptoms and season of delivery. Women delivering in the last 3 months of the year had a significantly higher risk of self-reported depressive symptomatology both at 6 weeks and at 6 months after delivery in comparison to those delivering April-June, both before and after adjustment for possible confounders. The author points out that Women delivering during the last quartile of the year had a significantly higher risk for depressive symptoms 6 weeks and 6 months postpartum and would thus benefit from a closer support and follow-up after delivery.

Sahابه Etebary, 2010 in the” study on Postpartum Depression and Role of Serum Trace Elements” The study aims to assess the role of trace elements including zinc, magnesium, iron andcopper in Postpartum Depression. Zinc as a trace element has the second highest concentration of all transition metals in the brain, and its deficiency is associated with behavioral disturbances. The study points out that Lower zinc blood concentration was found in women with postpartum depression. Other trace element like magnesium also influences the nervous system via its actions on the release and metabolism of neurotransmitters. Antidepressant -like effects of magnesium and its deficiency has been reported in depression.

Data Analysis And Interpretation

After collecting the data according to the purpose and objectives of the study, the data collected were organized, classified, coded, tabulated and analyzed and interpreted.

other 28% of the respondents were in the age group of above 30years, 13.3% are in between 18 – 20 years and remaining 3% are less than 18 years.

Figure No.1 Age of respondents

Table No.2 Distribution of age of the infant

Age of the infant	No. of respondents	Percentage
1-3 weeks	10	17
1-3 months	19	32
4-7 months	13	21
8-12 months	18	30
Total	60	100

It shows that out of the total 60 respondents 32% of them were under the age group of 1– 3months, other 30% of the respondents were in the age of 8 –

12 months, 21% are in between 1– 3 months and reaming 17% are in 1-3 weeks

Figure 2 Age of the infant

Table No.3 Distribution of education of the respondents

Qualification	No. of respondents	Percentage
Secondary	14	23
Degree and above	46	77
Total	60	100

The above diagram shows the Educational Qualification of the respondents. It shows that out of the 60 respondents 77% of them are found to be

completed degree and above, and only 23% of them had secondary education.

Figure No.3 Educational Qualification

Table No. 4 Distribution of occupation of the respondents

Occupation	No. of respondent	Percentage
Unemployed	19	32
Government sector	14	23
Agriculture	11	18
Private sector	16	27
Total	60	100

As the above table shows the occupation of the respondents, 32% are unemployed, 27% are working in private sector, 23% are employed in government sector and 18% is doing agricultural works.

Figure 4 Occupation of the respondents

Table No. 5 Distribution of expectation of the child

Expected child	No. of respondents	Percentage
Yes	25	42
No	35	58
Total	60	100

As the above table shows expectation of the child, 58% were not expecting the child now and 42% were expected the child.

Figure 5 Expectation of child

Table No .6 Distribution of type of delivery

Type of delivery	No. of respondents	Percentage
Caesarean	26	43
Normal	34	57
Total	60	100

As the above table shows the type of delivery, 57% are normal delivery, while 43% are caesarean.

Figure No.6 Type of delivery

Table No. 7 Representation of the Prevalence of postpartum Depression

Postpartum depression	No. of respondents	Percentage
Having depression	28	47
Not having depression	32	53
Total	60	100

As the above table shows, the prevalence of postpartum depression among women. 53% of respondents have no depression while 47% of the respondents suffer from depression.

Figure No. Prevalence of Postpartum Depression

Findings, Suggestions And Conclusion

1. Majority of the respondents (77%) are found to be graduated or post graduated.
2. More than half of the respondents (55%) are from an age group of 20-30 years.
3. 78% of the respondents are working women
4. 76% of the respondents draw a monthly income below 10000 –20000.
5. 86.7% of the population have access to health service
6. 51.7% of the respondents will go for check-up once in a month
7. Majority of respondents (88.3 %) did not suffer any complication during pregnancy
8. 58.3% of respondents had no expectation of child
9. Half of the respondents children (30%) were female while other 30% was male
10. Majority of the respondents (85%) are in normal weight
11. 66.7% of the population uses betel leaves
12. Least percentage of the respondents (5%) is using substance.
13. 13% of the respondents had a history of depression.
14. Nearly half of the respondents (47%) are feeling scary or panic
15. Majority (35%) of the respondents are been anxious or worried for no good reason.
16. Majority (53%) of the respondents are unhappy because of the difficulty in sleeping.
17. 28% of the respondents felt sad or miserable.
18. Tendency to self-harm was also found among the respondents which covers 30% of the total population
19. Majority (85%) of the respondents have good quality of life.
20. Majority 71.6% of the respondents are able accept their bodily appearance
21. 37% of the respondent having negative feelings and 35% respondents have negative feelings in seldom.

22. Nearly half of the respondents 47% are prevailing with postpartum depression among women.

Suggestions

1. During the time of pregnancy and after delivery doctors can recommend postpartum check up to screen for the signs and symptoms of depression.
2. Mild symptomatic depressions can be treated by using psychotherapies like talk therapy.
3. Proper counseling can help the respondents to get away from depression.
4. Relaxation techniques can be used

Conclusion

Even in the 21st century attitude of people towards mental illness is very pathetic. This is due to lack of education, awareness, and stigma towards various mental illnesses. Postpartum depression is one such mental illness which people are totally ignorant off. Prevalence of postpartum depression was found to be 47% among women in Pathanamthitta district, Kerala. Since the statistics is seen to be higher in the urban/rural people it is significant to take initiatives to overcome postpartum depression. It is also identified that close association of various elements can be recognized as a risk factor of PPD. Taking appropriate measures to mitigate these factors may function as an effective tool to eliminate PPD. Hence, if proper awareness and education is not provided, it can lead to severe consequences which may include homicides and suicides.

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